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Temperature Mediated Changes in Agrobacterium-Groundnut Transformation System

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ABSTRACT

Agrobacterium-Groundnut was selected as a model transformation system in order to study abiotic stress tolerance in higher plants. Co-cultivation with a good transformation frequency (75%) supported temperature mediated acclimation of the system in terms of stress related proteins and amino acid proline as well.

Keywords: Agrobacterium transformation, Groundnut, temperature stress.

Plants are seldom exposed in nature to only one type of stress. In arid and semi-arid environments, chilling and heat stresses on the seed-bank are often coupled with the impact of microbes in the soil and / or on emerging embryos and growing seedlings. While there is a plethora of studies on the effect of either thermal or Agrobacterial infection on plants, investigations of the combined effect of the two stresses are rare. Thermal stress (Whether chilling or heating) and/or microbial infections are known induce a number of physiological responses in plants, including changes in protein pattern, amino acid profile of the stressed plants, which ultimately affected the growth. Abiotic stress cause deleterious changes in many enzymes and structural proteins such as denaturation and aggregation of non-native proteins [1].

'In vitro' cultured Agrobacterium- plant co-cultures of transformation system can be induced to undergo developmental switch by certain physical and chemical stress treatments. Our knowledge about the metabolic profiles of stress induced co-culture is still restricted. A more detailed insight could be highly beneficial to resolve co-culture reprogramming

difficulties in so-called recalcitrant species. . About 95% of the cultivated areas of Groundnut (*Arachis hypogea* L.), one of the principal oilseed legume are in semi- arid tropics, where day time temperature often exceed 35°C, during flowering and appears an ideal system for studying temperature fluctuation related response. Physiological changes in development can, amongst other methods, be assisted by metabolic profile. It allows quantitative and qualitative measurement of low molecular weight compounds or specific metabolic pathways in cells, tissues or in the whole plant [2]. The influence of heat and drought was studied on Arabidopsis by analyzing both differential gene expression and metabolic profiles. About 50 transcripts were specifically expressed and plants accumulated high levels of sucrose and other sugars [3].

In the present study an 'in vitro' experiment was designed to stimulate the thermal conditions of arid and semi-arid environments by exposing Agrobacterium - groundnut co-cultures to chilling or heating in order to investigate the effects of these stresses on transformation frequency and to obtain a more integral understanding of the cellular reprogramming in

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groundnut co-cultures.

Materials and Methods:

The local groundnut was collected from farmers of Biharigarh, Gateway Doon valley. Seeds were cleaned, surface sterilized with 0.2% HgCl₂ and washed with distilled water. Then the seeds were imbibed in water for 6-8 hours and then aseptically cultivated in half strength MS media. After germination the cotyledons of 7 days old seedlings were used as explants for the transformation process through co-cultivation of native soil Agrobacterial isolate.

A large scale screening was conducted in order to isolate

Agrobacterium from the native soil samples. Soil samples were serially diluted and proper dilutions were spread onto 1A[4], 2E and MGY [5] semi selective media (Table 1.0) by pour plating technique. The colonies were selected and purified on PDA slants, supplemented with 0.5% w/v calcium carbonate for further characterization. On strain GE1 was identified as Agrobacterium.

The cotyledons were cultured on embryo induction media (MS medium supplemented with 0.5 mg/l NAA and 10.0 mg/l BAP) and further recultured with Agrobacterium in order to get co-cultures on the embryo induction media with antibiotics (50 µg/ml Kanamycin and 300 µg/ml cefotaxime). Co-cultures were subjected to varying temperature regimes and temperature mediated metabolic profiles were analyzed in terms of cytoplasmic proteins, qualitatively [6] and quantitatively [7] and free proline content [8].

All the experiments were carried out at biotechnology department, Sardar Bhagwan Singh (PG) Institute of Biomedical Sciences and Research, Dehradun, during 2007-2008.

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Fig 1: Production of 3-Keto maltose by Ge1

Fig. 2: SDS-PAGE profile of Agrobacterial cytosolic Proteins at different temperature (°C) regimes

Result and Discussion:

Soil bacteria were screened and characterized as per the standard protocols given in materials and methods. On the basis of characteristic response as given in table 2.0, one strain GE1 was identified as Agrobacterium (Fig1).

Seeds of Doon Valley cultivar of groundnut were allowed to germinate on half strength MS media [9] under aseptic 'in vitro' conditions. Frequency of germination was recorded as percentage of germination and found to be ca. ≈ 60%. Good germination efficacy of Doon valley cultivated seeds favoured the suitability of their selection as a source of explants for Agrobacterium mediated transformation studies (Table 3.0).

GE1 inoculated groundnut cotyledons (transformation system) along with controls (explants and GE1 separately) were allowed to proliferate on kanamycin containing selective half strength MS media. All the cultures were recultured for further studies. Recultured co-cultivated transformation system was further evaluated in terms of survival percentage. Kanamycin sensitivity of cotyledon explants was assessed prior to Agrobacterium transformation. 50 µg/ml kanamycin was found to be sufficient for killing all the cells of explants in absence of co-cultivation. However, media allowed a quite good frequency of transformation (ca. ≈ 75%) in case of co-cultivation of the system. One of the critical factors of achieving high transformation frequency is related to preculturing of explants on the embryo induction medium prior to co-cultivation. After selection through a two-day preculture, healthy cotyledons were infected and co-cultivated.

All the cultures were subjected to varying

temperature regimes and analyzed in terms of abiotic stress related proteins and amino acid proline in order to judge stress acclimation of the transformation system (Table 5.0 and 6.0). Special emphasis was put on the bacterial component because higher plants, in general, do not depend on small temperature changes when responding to such pathogen. [10].

A general increase, as compared to control, was observed in cytoplasmic protein content of the cultures shifted from normal (30°C) to low temperature regimes (20°C and 15°C). Protein content was found to be reduced in all the cultures under extreme levels of cold stress (-20°C). However, cytoplasmic proteins of uninoculated as well as co-cultivated cultures remained more or less unaffected due to the heat shock treatment.

In general, co-cultivation supports the stress acclimation of cells in transformation system. Temperature regimes increased the proline content (1.5-3 times) of the cultures tested. When compared with control, uninoculated as well as co-cultivated explant cultures were found to be accumulated more proline under cold stress as compared to heat shock condition (40°C). Interestingly, proline accumulation seemed to be unaffected due to the co-cultivation and favours its temperature mediated induction in transformation system.

17 polypeptides of molecular weight 66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 29, 27, 24, 20, 14, 11, 9 and 5 kDa were resolved on 10% SDS-Polyacrylamide gels in GE1 culture at normal temperature (30°C). These polypeptides remained common but with low intensity at cold temperatures of 20°C and 15°C. However, high molecular weight polypeptides of 100, 97 and 95 kDa were appeared and low molecular weight polypeptides of 14 and 11 kDa were disappeared at both extremes (-20°C and 40°C) of temperature stress. Besides, polypeptides of molecular weight 29, 27, 24 and 20 were also disappeared at heat shock conditions, which reflect the severity of the stress towards synthesis of low molecular weight polypeptides. (Fig. 2 and Table 7.0).

Our results of the current study support the literature available on studies related to plant-microbe

interactions under stress conditions [10][11] [12][13] [14][15] [16]. Research over the past two decade, has provided a better understanding of the molecular biology of stress responses in plants. Many genes and gene products have been identified, which get induced upon exposure to plants to various abiotic stresses, Salinity, draught, low and high temperature stress etc. Consequently biotechnological tools have been applied to transfer some of these useful genes implicated in stress tolerance to plants. Indeed, transgenic plants provide an excellent system to overexpress stress induced proteins 'in vivo' and to access their function and tolerance conferred to them [17][18]. In addition to these stress induced proteins, genes encoding enzymes of the biosynthetic pathways of different osmolytes, such as proline, glycine betaine, sorbitol etc. have been cloned and exploited in improving stress tolerance in plants, through genetic engineering [19]. Present study may be the initiatory effort to this series.

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Table 1.0: Media Composition

Media	Constituent	Amount(g/L)
2E	Erythritol	3.06
	NH ₄ NO ₃	0.16
	KH ₂ PO ₄	0.54
	K ₂ HPO ₄	1.04
	Sodium tauro cholate	0.29
	MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.25
	Agar	15
	Malachite green (0.1%)	5.0 ml
	Yeast extract (1%w/v)	1.0 ml
	MGY	L(-) Glutamic acid(sodium salt)
NaCl		0.2
KH ₂ PO ₄		0.5
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O		0.02
Yeast extract		1.0
Agar		15

Table 2.0: Characterization of soil isolate Ge1

Biochemical tests	Response
Gram Staining	Gram negative
Simple staining	Short Rod
Endospore staining	No endospores
Oxidase	Negative
Simony citrate	Negative
Urease	Positive
Growth on 1A medium	Negative
Growth on 2E medium	Positive
Growth on MGY medium	Positive
Production of 3-Keto maltose	Positive

Media	Constituent	Amount(g/L)
1A	L(-) Arabinol	3.01
	NH ₄ NO ₃	0.16
	KH ₂ PO ₄	0.54
	K ₂ HPO ₄	1.04
	Sodium tauro cholate	0.145
	MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	0.25
	Agar	15
	Crystal violet (0.1%)	2.0 ml

Table 4.0: Transformation of putatively transformed callus of groundnut cotyledons cultured on MS media containing 2-4D (.0001 g/100ml) and Kanamycin (50µg/ml).

Experiment	No. of explants cultured	No. of explants responded	Response frequency
Control*	10	4	40%
Control**	10	0	-
Co-cultured	10	3	33%

*No co-cultivation, non selective medium (without kanamycin)

**No co-cultivation. Selective media (with kanamycin).

Table 5.0: Cytoplasmic protein estimation (µg/g) ***at different temperatures (°C). Values are mean of five observations ±S.D.

Experiment	No. of seeds cultured	No. of seeds responded	Frequency of germination
In vitro cultivation	12	7	58.33%

	-20	15	20	30	40
Un inoculated		2.3±0.076	2.49±0.082	1.65±0.088	1.80±0.058
Callus					
GEI	3.14±0.067	5.79±0.085	7.90±0.092	4.59±0.058	3.02±0.064
Co-culture	1.86±0.046	2.7±0.094	2.56±0.102	2.46±0.053	2.22±0.063

*** Average ±S.D. n=5

Table 6.0 Proline content (µg/g) ***at different temperatures (°C). Values are mean of five observations ±S.D.

Table 6.0: Proline content (µg/g) ***at different temperatures (°C). Values are mean of five observations ±S.D.

	-20	15	20	30	40
Un-inoculated callus	1.39±0.027	1.90±0.037	1.69±0.027	0.85±0.041	1.13±0.040
GEI	2.59±0.027	5.76±0.094	4.61±0.052	2.1±0.35	0.598±0.033
Co-cultured	1.71±0.033	2.17±0.053	1.59±0.014	0.88±0.044	1.30±0.06

*** Average ±S.D. n=5

Table 7.0: Profile of Agrobacterial cytosolic proteins

Temperature stress (°C)	Molecular weights of polypeptides
20	66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 29, 27, 24, 20, 14, 11, 9, 5
15	66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 29, 27, 24, 20, 14, 11, 9, 5
30	66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 29, 27, 24, 20, 14, 11, 9, 5
40	100, 97, 95, 66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 9, 5
-20	100, 97, 95, 66, 57, 52, 47, 44, 41, 36, 34, 32, 29, 27, 24, 20, 9, 5

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